

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

New Analytical Methods for Flame Retardants and Plasticizers Based on Gas Chromatography, Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Gas Chromatography and Direct Probe Coupled to Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization-High Resolution Time-of Flight-Mass Spectrometry

A. Ballesteros-Gómez*, J. de Boer, P. E.G. Leonards

Institute for Environmental Studies, VU University, De Boelelaan 1087, 1081 HV

Amsterdam, the Netherlands. Fax +31205989553, *e-mail:

anamaria.ballesterosgomez@vu.nl

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Chemicals

Standards of flame retardants were obtained from Wellington Laboratories (Guelph, Ontario, Canada), namely polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs, from tri- to decabromodiphenyl ether); tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA); α -, β -, and γ -hexabromocyclodecane (HBCD); allyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether (ATE); 2,3-dibromopropyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether (DPTE); bis(2-ethyl-1-hexyl)tetrabromophthalate (BEHTBP); decabromodiphenylethane (DBDPE); 1,2-bis(2,4,6-tribromophenoxy)ethane (BTBPE); hexachlorocyclopentenyl-dibromocyclooctane (HCDBCO); 2-ethylexyl-2,3,4,5-tetrabromobenzoate (EHTBB), 2-bromoallyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether (BATE) supplied in 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ampoules in nonane or toluene. Phosphorus flame retardants and plasticizers tris(butyl) phosphate (TNBP); tris(2-chloroisopropyl) phosphate (TCIPP); tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate (TBOEP); 2-ethylhexyldiphenyl phosphate (EHDP); 2-ethylhexyl phosphate (TEHP); tris(butoxyethyl) phosphate (TEHP) and tris(phenyl) phosphate (TPHP); tris(methylphenyl) phosphate (TMPP) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands); tris(isobutyl) phosphate (TiBP) from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP) from Dr. Ehrenstorfer Laboratories (Augsburg, Germany) and 3,4:5,6-dibenzo-2H-1,2-oxaphosphorin-2-oxide (DOPO) from Krems (KCCS, Austria). The internal standards (IS)15-TPHP and d27-TNBP were obtained from by respectively, Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands) and Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc. (Andover, MA, USA). Stock solutions were made at 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in toluene or and stored at 4°C and darkness. For all the compounds that were analysed in negative mode PBDE58 was used as IS while d15-TPHP was used as IS in

the positive mode for the analysis of phosphorus flame retardants except for TNBP, TiBP, TCEP and TCIPP for which d27-TNBP was used instead.

n-Hexane, acetone, methanol, toluene, iso-octane and acetonitrile were purchased from J.T. Baker (Deventer, the Netherlands) and dichloromethane (DCM) from Promochem (Wesel, Germany). Milli-Q water was obtained from ultrapure water purification Q-Pod system (Millipore, Bedford, USA). All solvents and reagents were of analytical grade and used as supplied.

For calibration purposes a mixture of fatty acids (C₅-C₂₉) obtained individually from Larodan AB (Malmö, Sweden) was prepared at a concentration of 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ in toluene and stored at 4°C. The final calibration solution for both APCI and APPI was made by dilution of the stock fatty acid solution 1:2 (v/v) with an APCI-TOF tuning mix provided by Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). Typical ions originating from the stationary phase and common interferences in MS were also included in the calibration list. For internal calibration, HPC (high precision *calibration*) and enhanced quadratic mode were used for masses lower and higher than 600 m/z, respectively. Calibration was done by introducing the calibration solution into the system with a syringe pump directly into the source through the sprayer port before each batch of experiments and within each run in the first minute of the chromatogram by means of a switching valve. The calibration solution was collected from the waste port and recycled. The configuration of the switching valve designed for use with LC by the equipment supplier was changed for making it suitable with GC. Details are given in Table S-5.

Instrumentation

A microTOF II (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) with optimal mass accuracy <2ppm and resolution >16,500 FWHM was used as detector and equipped with the following commercially available sources: APPI source, LC-APCI II source, direct probe injection assembly, GC-APCI source and electrospray (ESI) source, all of them supplied by Bruker. Values of mass accuracy during sample analysis with internal calibration and operation conditions employed were below 5 ppm. An Agilent 1220 Infinity HPLC and an Agilent 890A GC, the latter equipped with an Agilent differential flow modulator for GCxGC experiments and an Agilent micro-ECD, that was used for GC and GCxGC column selection (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA), were employed prior to detection.

A Kinetex core-shell LC C18 column (2.1 mm x 100mm x 2.6 μ m) was obtained from Phenomenex (Torrance, California). Different GC capillary columns were tested for both GC and GCxGC (as first column) (dimensions 15 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μ m, except for ionic liquids columns with a film thickness of 0.2 μ m instead), namely BPX1 (100% dimethyl polysiloxane) from SGE Europe Ltd. (Milton Keynes, United Kingdom), two high temperature columns: ZB-HLB-HT Inferno (low polarity silarene) and ZB-35HT Inferno (35% phenyl 65% dimethyl polysiloxane) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA), an Rxi-200 (trifluoropropylmethyl polysiloxane) column from Restek (Bellefonte, PA, USA) and the ionic liquid columns SLB-IL59, SLB-IL60 from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). For the second dimension the following columns with dimensions of 5m x 0.25 mm x 0.1 μ m were tested: polar polyethylene glycol (PEG) columns, namely HP-Innowax from J&W Scientific (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) and megaWAX from Mega (Legnano, MI, Italy), a medium polar column 007-65HT (65% phenyl 35% dimethyl polysiloxane) from Quadrex (Woodbridge, CT,

USA) and the non-polar DB-5 (5% phenyl dimethyl polysiloxane) from J&W Scientific (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA).

The software data analysis 4.0 and quant analysis 2.0 from Bruker Daltonics (Bremen, Germany) were used, for screening and quantification. Dissection, smart formula and compound crawler tools of data analysis 4.0 were employed for untargeted screening. The dissection tool extracts the chromatograms of the most abundant ions, smart formula provides identification on the basis of accurate mass and isotopic pattern and compound crawler connects with online accurate mass databases (e.g. Metlin, Chempider) for formula identification. GC Image 2.3 software from LLC (Lincoln, NE, USA) was employed for building 2D and 3D plots from GCxGC-HRTOF-MS data. For GCxGC data acquisition, the profile spectra option was deactivated and centroid spectra were collected, and the scanning mass range was set at 200-950 m/z to reduce the file size. Experiments made with the option Focus for enhanced resolution activated. The acquisition rate was set at 25 Hz. Interpolation was done with the option *nearest neighbour* and a threshold intensity filter of 100 was used for building the image.

For sample treatment micro-centrifuge filters (0.2 μm , nylon) from Costar Spin-X obtained from Sigma-Aldrich were used for removing micro-particles from sample extracts.

Figure S-1. GC-ECD chromatograms for PBDEs mix and new flame retardants with different GC columns (dimensions: 15 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μ m). Temperature program: 90 $^{\circ}$ C for 3 min, to 170 $^{\circ}$ C at a ramp of 15 $^{\circ}$ C min^{-1} and to 320 $^{\circ}$ C at a ramp of 5 $^{\circ}$ C min^{-1} ; flow 1 mL min^{-1} He

Figure S-2. GCxGC-ECD chromatograms with different column combinations: A) Rxi-200-megaWAX; temperature program: 90 °C (hold 3 min), 15 °C min⁻¹ to 175 °C, then 3 °C min⁻¹ to 300 °C (hold 30 min); flow 1st dimension 0.4 mL min⁻¹; flow 2nd dimension 35 mL min⁻¹; make-up flow ECD 80 mL min⁻¹; B) Rxi-200 -Zebron35HT; temperature program: 90°C (hold 3 min), 15 °C min⁻¹ to 175 °C, then 3 °C min⁻¹ to 300 °C (hold 30 min); flow 1st dimension 0.4 mL min⁻¹; flow 2nd dimension 50 mL min⁻¹, make-up flow ECD 100 mL min⁻¹ ; secondary oven offset at 20 °C; C) Rxi-200 -DB5; temperature program: 90 °C (hold 3 min), 15 °C min⁻¹ to 200 °C, then 3 C min⁻¹ to 310 °C (hold 30 min); flow 1st dimension: 0.5 mL min⁻¹; flow 2nd dimension 50 mL min⁻¹, make-up flow ECD 100 mL min⁻¹; secondary oven offset at 20 °C, except for final temperature set at 315 °C

Figure S-3. (A) GCxGC chromatogram and (B) insert of 1D chromatogram showing modulated peaks for the extracted ion chromatograms of BDE153 and a co-eluting interferent in GCxGC-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS analysis of the sample e-waste 1

Table S-1. Flame retardants and plasticizers (name, structure, molecular formula), main and secondary confirmation ion in GC-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS and retention times in GC and GCxGC

Target Compound	Structure	Molecular Formula	Main Ion		Secondary Ion		GC (RT, min)	GCxGC (RT)		
			Ion	^a Accurate mass	Ion	^a Accurate mass		1D (min)	2D (sec)	
BDE28	2,4,4'-Tribromodiphenylether		C ₁₂ H ₇ Br ₃ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	342.87982	[M-HBr+O ₂] ⁻	357.86583	9.32	28.87	0.49
BDE 47	2,2',4,4'-Tetrabromodiphenyl ether		C ₁₂ H ₆ Br ₄ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	420.79032	[M-HBr+O ₂] ⁻	435.77632	10.83	34.56	0.54
BDE 99	2,2',4,4',5-Pentabromodiphenyl ether		C ₁₂ H ₅ Br ₅ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	500.69882	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	516.69265	12.38	40.23	0.59
BDE 153	2,2',4,4',5,5'-Hexabromodiphenyl ether		C ₁₂ H ₄ Br ₆ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	578.60932	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	594.60315	13.93	45.87	0.65
BDE 183	2,2',3,4,4',5',6-Heptabromodiphenylether		C ₁₂ H ₃ Br ₇ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	658.51781	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	674.51163	14.92	50.43	1.19
BDE 203	2,2',3,4,4',5,5',6-Octabromodiphenylether		C ₁₂ H ₂ Br ₈ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	736.42831	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	752.42323	15.99	57.42	2.43
BDE 206	2,2',3,3',4,4',5,5',6-Nonabromodiphenylether		C ₁₂ HBr ₉ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	816.33679	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	832.33172	17.11	67.95	1.14
BDE 209	Decabromodiphenyl ether		C ₁₂ Br ₁₀ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	894.24729	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	910.24112	17.85	-	-
ATE	Allyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether		C ₉ H ₇ Br ₃ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	306.87872	-	-	6.17	19.83	0.39
BATE	2-Bromoallyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether		C ₉ H ₆ Br ₄ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	384.78922	[M-HBr+O ₂] ⁻	399.77631	8.08	24.70	0.43
DPTE	2,3-Dibromopropyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether		C ₉ H ₇ Br ₅ O	[M-Br+O] ⁻	466.71336	[M+O ₂] ⁻	561.62660	10.46	33.33	0.49
HCDBCO	Hexachlorocyclopentenyl-dibromocyclooctane		C ₁₃ H ₁₂ Br ₂ C ₁₆	[M-Cl+O] ⁻	520.76426	[M-Br+O] ⁻	571.72796	12.76	42.53	0.60
EHTBB	2-Ethylexyl-2,3,4,5-tetrabromobenzoate		C ₁₅ H ₁₈ Br ₄ O ₂	[M-Br+O] ⁻	484.87806	[M- Br+O ₂] ⁻	500.87298	12.89	42.03	0.38
TBBPA	3,3',5,5'-Tetrabromobisphenol A		C ₁₅ H ₁₂ Br ₄ O ₂	[M-H] ⁻	542.74470	[M-Br+O ₂] ⁻	478.83111	14.69	49.08	0.54
α-β-δ-HBCD	1,2,5,6,9,10-Hexabromocyclododecane		C ₁₂ H ₁₈ Br ₆	[M-H] ⁻	642.65206	[M-Br+O] ⁻	576.72285	15.18	-	-
BTBPE	Bis(2,4,6-tribromophenoxy)ethane		C ₁₄ H ₈ Br ₆ O ₂	Fragment C ₆ Br ₃ H ₂ O ⁻	328.76298	[M+O ₂] ⁻	719.54571	15.43	53.49	1.29
BEHTBP	bis(2-Ethyl-1-hexyl)tetrabromophthalate		C ₂₄ H ₃₄ Br ₄ O ₄	[M-Br+O] ⁻	642.99109	[M- Br+O ₂] ⁻	658.98602	16.01	56.57	1.51

^aAccurate mass values calculated with Compass Isotope pattern from Data analysis 4.0 (Bruker Daltonics)

Table S-2. Flame retardants and plasticizers (name, structure, molecular formula), main and secondary confirmation ion in GC-APCI(+)-HRTOF-MS and retention times in GC and GCxGC

Target Compound	Structure	Molecular Formula	Main Ion		Secondary Ion		GC (RT, min)	GCxGC (RT)		
			Ion	^a Accurate mass	Ion	^a Accurate mass		1D (min)	2D (sec)	
TIBP	Tris(isobutyl) phosphate		C ₁₂ H ₂₇ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	267.1719	-	-	6.08	15.1	3.67
TNBP	Tris(butyl) phosphate		C ₁₂ H ₂₇ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	267.1719	-	-	6.93	17.28	3.67
TCEP	Tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate		C ₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	284.9612	-	-	8.13	22.22	3.78
TCIPP	Tris(1-chloro-2-propanyl) phosphate		C ₉ H ₁₈ Cl ₃ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	327.0081	-	-	8.15 8.29	22.15 22.35	3.78 3.73
DOPO	3,4,5,6-Dibenzo-2H-1,2-oxaphosphorin-2-oxide		C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ P	[M+H] ⁺	217.0413	-	-	11.85	38.15	3.94
TPHP	tris(phenyl) phosphate		C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	327.0781	-	-	12.46	37.75	0.16
EHDP	2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate		C ₂₀ H ₂₇ O ₄ P	[M-C ₈ H ₁₇ +H ₂]	251.0468	[M+H] ⁺	363.17197	12.73	37.88	0.22
TEHP	2-Ethylhexyl phosphate		C ₂₄ H ₅₁ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	435.3598	-	-	12.95	37.15	0.27
TBOEP	Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate		C ₁₈ H ₃₉ O ₇ P	[M+H] ⁺	399.2506	-	-	13.04	37.49	0.11
TMPP	Tris(methylphenyl) phosphate		C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ P	[M+H] ⁺	369.1250	-	-	16.64 17.25 17.91	48.89 50.82 50.89	0.82 0.99 1.48

^aAccurate mass values calculated with Compass Isotope pattern from Data analysis 4.0 (Bruker Daltonics)

For TMPP and TCIPP the retention times of the first three and two isomers, respectively are given (only the first eluting isomer was used for quantification)

Table S-3. LC-HRTOF-MS parameters

System	Chromatographic separation conditions	¹TOF parameters
LC-APCI-HRTOF	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Core-shell C₁₈ column (2.1 mm x 100 mm 2.6 μm)• Mobile phase: 0.3 mL min⁻¹ water : methanol in gradient• Injection volume: 5 μL	Capillary (neg./pos.) -/+1000 V End plate offset (neg.) -1000 (pos.) -500 Corona (neg.) -10000 nA(pos.) +6000 nA Dry gas 4 L min ⁻¹ Nebulizer 3 bar Dry Heater 285 °C Vaporizer temperature 285 °C
LC-APPI-HRTOF	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Core-shell C₁₈ column (2.1 mm x 100 mm 2.6 μm)• Mobile phase: 0.3 mL min⁻¹ water : methanol in gradient• Injection volume: 5 μL• Dopant: 40 μL min⁻¹ toluene (introduced through an additional gas port in the source)	Capillary (neg./posit.) -/+700 V End plate offset (neg./pos.) -500 Dry gas 4 L min ⁻¹ Nebulizer 3 bar Dry Heater 285 °C Vaporizer temperature 285 °C
LC-ESI(-)-HRTOF	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Core-shell C₁₈ column (2.1 mm x 100 mm 2.6 μm)• Mobile phase: 0.3 mL min⁻¹ water : methanol in gradient• Injection volume: 5 μL	Capillary (neg.) -4500 V End plate offset (neg.) -500 Dry gas 6 L min ⁻¹ Nebulizer 4 bar Dry Heater 250 °C Vaporizer temperature 250 °C

¹TOF detection parameters: capillary exit: ±80 V; Skimmer1: ±26.7 V; Hexapole RF: 250 V (negative mode) and 200 V (positive mode); transfer time: 40; puls storage time: 10; focus on

Table S-4. GC performance of the different capillary columns tested

Stationary phase	number of co-elutions	^a Relative intensity, ^b retention time (min) and ^c width (min) (BDE153/decaBDE); individual values in brackets ^d Relative retention time (min) (BDE153/BTBPE); individual values in brackets
^e 100% Dimethyl polysiloxane (BPX1)	BDE 153+TBBPA	^a 1.20 ^b 0.65 (25.901/39.995) ^c 0.65(0.065/0.1) ^d 0.86 (25.901/29.953)
^f Low polarity sylarene (ZB-XLB-HT Inferno)	BDE 71+BDE 49 EHTBB+BDE 99 BDE 138-HBCD BDE 153+TBBPA	^a 2.14 ^b 1.74 (30.629/52.932) ^c 0.17 (0.069/0.398) ^d 0.87 (30.629/35.162)
^g (35% Phenyl)-65% dimethyl polysiloxane (ZB-35HT Inferno)	BDE 153+TBBPA	^a 1.68 ^b 0.51 (29.874/58.045) ^c 0.182 (0.049/0.269) ^d 0.93 (29.874/32.275)
^h Trifluoropropylmethyl polysiloxane ^b (Rxi-200)	BDE 196+BEHTBP	^a 1.12 ^b 0.59 (28.284/48.212) ^c 0.75 (0.066/0.088) ^d 0.80 (28.284/35.135)
Ionic liquid columns (SLB- ⁱ IL59, ^j SLB-IL60)	Degradation for BDEs \geq hexaBDEs	

Temperature program :^e90°C (hold 3min), at 15 °C min⁻¹ to 170 °C, then at 5 °C min⁻¹ to 320 °C (hold 25 min); ^f90 °C (hold 3min), at 20 °C min⁻¹ to 200 °C, at 5 °C min⁻¹ to 320 °C, at 20 °C min⁻¹ to 330 °C (hold 25 min); ^g90 °C (hold 3min), at 15 °C min⁻¹ to 170°C, then at 3 °C min⁻¹ to 320 °C (hold 25 min); ^h90 °C (hold 3min), at 20 °C min⁻¹ to 225 °C, then at 3 °C min⁻¹ to ⁱ300 °C or ^j290 °C (hold 35 min)

Table S-5. Switching valve position and time segments in the MS program for LC and GC or GCxGC-APCI HR-TOF

	LC-APCI-HR-TOF^a	GC/GCxGC-APCI-HR-TOF
Port 1	From syringe pump	Loop 20 μ L
Port 2	Loop 20 μ L	-
Port 3	From LC	To MS source
Port 4	To MS source	From srynge pump
Port 5	Loop	Loop
Port 6	To waste	To waste
Flow	1 μ L min^{-1}	3 μ L min^{-1}
Time segments	0-0.02 min (to waste); 0.02-0.4 min (to source); >0.4 min (to waste)	Last two minutes of the chromatogram sent to source and the rest to waste

^aConfiguration as provided by Bruker Daltonics